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CASE STUDY

POSSIBILITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR LANDSCAPE OBSERVATORIES

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Abstract – The twentieth century saw rapid environmental degradation due to changes that contributed to increased net GHG emissions, loss of natural ecosystems, and declining biodiversity. Deterioration of unprotected landscapes during swift industrialization, urbanization, increasing monocultures in agriculture, expansion of commercial production significantly contributed to these negative consequences. However, a cultural shift occurred during the last two decades in favour of landscape conservation. In response to widespread landscape degradation and loss of ecosystem services, the Council of Europe saw the need to protect, manage, and develop the landscapes, and thus signed the European Landscape Convention (ELC) in 2000. This was the world's first international agreement that described all aspects of landscape management in detail. The European Landscape Convention fully meets the challenges through its goal of correcting a lack of understanding of landscapes as a unique system embracing natural, economic, and social features throughout Europe. It goes beyond simply protecting landscapes and addresses landscape management and development, as well as raising public and government awareness of the importance of paying attention to all types of landscapes, whether exceptional or spoiled. Landscape observatories, multifunctional platforms and knowledge centres for researchers, technicians, administrators, and citizens, are one of the Council of Europe's instruments for implementing the European Landscape Convention (ELC). They can be established on a variety of scales and can serve as a vital link between administrations, civil society, researchers, and the economic sector. This article discusses the emergence of landscape observatories and the role they can play as decision support instruments in promoting sustainable landscape development through a regenerative approach. Additionally, the paper discusses the implementation of ELC in Västra Götaland in Sweden through the establishment of Landscape Observatory Västra Götaland, and its impacts and challenges associated with landscape development. Furthermore, we propose a comprehensive and holistic, to any landscape type adaptable landscape observatory concept, based on multifunctionality of these institutions, emphasizing their decision support roles, social and economic importance.

Keywords – landscape observatories, ecosystem services, decision support systems, climate change, land use, biodiversity, earth system science, heritage conservation, ecomuseum, nature-based solutions, stakeholder management, sustainability education

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INTRODUCTION

In this study, the emergence of landscape observatories and their role in creating modern, ecosystem centred regional development policies, regenerative landscape management systems, and mitigation of the adverse impacts of climate change and anthropogenic activities is discussed. Lessons learned in terms of organizational forms and content from various types of landscape observatories are discussed, as well as how these can be applied in Scandinavia and elsewhere in Europe. This is to gain a better understanding of the functions of observatories, as well as how they can be developed to play an important bridging role in society by

connecting the general public, businesses, civil organisations and political decision makers. The case study Landscape Observatory Västra Götaland is described, as well as the components required for its further development.

In order to understand and illustrate the complexity and the usefulness of landscape observatories, the following subject areas will be addressed in this study:

1. The emergence of landscape observatories in Europe – European Landscape Convention
2. The types of landscape observatories and the roles they can play in sustainable landscape management
3. Landscape types and land use

4. Functions, and challenges for landscape observatories – applied Earth System Science as a tool
5. International good practices and their adaptability
6. Optimal structure of landscape observatories – an interdisciplinary multifunctional model
 - a. Landscape observatories and ecological resiliency in view of climate change
 - b. Landscape observatories as political decision support systems
 - c. The social function of landscape observatories: how to prevent or reverse the depopulation of rural areas
 - d. Landscape observatories as tools for green urban development
 - e. Integrating tourism and landscape conservation: ecomuseums – history and recent development
 - f. Landscape observatories as research institutes and resource centres for landscape ecology and conservation – creating interdisciplinary databases.

THE EMERGENCE OF LANDSCAPE OBSERVATORIES IN EUROPE

The twentieth century saw rapid environmental pollution, including significant loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services such as food security, water treatment, and energy provision (IPBES report 2018). According to the IPBES report, the primary global driver of land degradation is agricultural expansion and unsustainable landscape management, which is fuelled by unprecedented levels of consumption in an increasingly globalized economy. Furthermore, it states that land degradation is a significant contributor to climate change, with deforestation alone accounting for roughly 10% of all human-caused greenhouse gas emissions. According to the IPCC report (2020), the land surface air temperature has risen nearly twice as much as the global average temperature since the pre-industrial period. Climate change, including increases in the frequency and intensity of extreme events, has harmed food security and terrestrial ecosystems while also contributing to desertification and land degradation in many regions. Prokopová et al. (2018) concludes that the major trajectories of landscape transformation in Eastern Europe were linked to socioeconomic processes like urbanization, agricultural intensification, and cropland abandonment. Another example is the Mediterranean, which has undergone rapid transformation, resulting in fragility as a result of abnormal urban growth, increased tourism, overcrowded urban coastlines, and the abandonment of cultural practices. (Trovato G.M. and Abunnaser Y, 2015). Looking at the urbanization and the evolution of land exploitation over time, it is easy to understand it has impacted landscapes. According to Wu, J. (2010), in 1800, only 2% of the world's population lived in cities, but by 2007, this figure had risen to 50%. According to the UN, this figure is expected to rise to 75% within the next fifty years (United Nations, 2019). If this rate of urbanization is not properly managed, it will continue to have serious environmental, economic, and social consequences for the landscape.

The Council of Europe recognized the critical need to protect, manage, and develop the landscape to avoid continued negative effects of exploitation and development. In 2000,

The European Landscape Convention (ELC) was established by the Council with the goal of encouraging public authorities to implement landscape policies and measures at the local, regional, national, and international levels (ELC 2016). The Convention prioritises the preservation of mature vegetation, recognizing that it takes time to establish landscapes capable of supporting a diverse range of plants and animals. Additionally, they argue that a well-maintained landscape can boost local economic growth while also improving people's quality of life.

According to the ELC (2016), an effective and efficient way to work with landscape protection, management, and planning, is to continuously observe the landscape by available forums, such as landscape observatories (LOs). The Council of Europe's "Recommendation on the Guidelines for the Implementation of the European Landscape Convention" (Council of Europe, 2008) details what landscape observatories should do and how they should be organized. This can be summarised as follows:

- to recognize landscapes as a necessary component of people's surroundings, an expression of the diversity of their shared cultural and natural heritage, and a foundation of their identity,
- to develop and implement landscape policies aimed at landscape protection, management, and planning through specific measures outlined in Article 6,
- establish procedures for the general public, local and regional governments, and other parties with an interest in the definition and implementation of the landscape policies mentioned in the preceding paragraph,
- to incorporate landscape into its regional and town planning policies, as well as its cultural, environmental, agricultural, social, and economic policies, and any other policies that may have a direct or indirect impact on landscape.

Based on above guidelines, landscape observatories can be conceived in many ways. It is up to each observatory how to set up their system, but there are common activities, which are indispensable for their functions, such as databases of landscape information and materials (e. g. cartography, pictures and other types of iconographic representation, texts, communication platforms, etc.). More comprehensive materials developed by several observatories include landscape atlases. They aim to systematically monitor the processes and dynamics affecting the landscape and encourage participation in the management of landscape resources. Another critical role of the landscape observatory is to serve as a knowledge-based hub, bringing together experts, civil society, public officials, and decision makers to foster a shared understanding of the landscape, as well as to mediate, educate, and develop innovative initiatives. (Larcher F, Cassatella C, 2015).

THE TYPES OF LANDSCAPE OBSERVATORIES AND THE ROLES THEY CAN PLAY IN SUSTAINABLE LANDSCAPE MANAGEMENT

The Convention proposes legal and financial measures aimed at promoting interaction between local and central authorities as well as trans-frontier cooperation in protecting landscapes.

It sets out a range of different solutions which States can apply, according to their specific needs. Cassatella and Larcher (2017), divided landscape observatories into four main categories based on their organizational structure and activity level:

1. An organisation maintaining a database (or “data-container”) of material (cartography, photographs, texts, list of archaeological sites, all other types of iconographic representation), and immaterial knowledge; often referred to as a landscape atlas, which can be in printed or digital form;
2. Civil or scientific organisation functioning as a monitoring instrument for tracing and documenting long term landscape transformations;
3. A formal or informal forum, a meeting point between experience-based knowledge and experts-based knowledge, such as civil societies and experts, public officials, decision makers trying to jointly build up a communication platform based on a common language and mutually accepted values;
4. An organisation acting as mediator, catalyser, incubator of innovations, based more on people with more or less common values than on well-defined landscape types;

Regarding their way of organisation landscape observatories can be divided in two main categories:

1. *The bottom-up model*

This includes mostly local groups and associations voluntarily made, that are created and managed by people who are sensitive to landscape issues. These observatories are based on a model of involvement of the people from below, in which the “Know-how of experts” interacts with the “common Know-how” of the people. (Marco Devecchi 2015). This “bottom up” model shows a strong tendency towards the creation of networks includes mostly local groups and voluntary associations. Examples of bottom-up initiatives combined with civic participation are the Italian local landscape observatories, such as those in Piedmont and Venetia.

2. *The top-down model*

The opposite approach is the top-down initiatives with the Catalan Landscape Observatory, Observatori del Païsatge as an example. They combine top-down with civic participation to achieve success.

Several landscape observatories in Netherlands have stated that management and planning is best organised on a regional scale (Veen P.J., 2015). This is connected to that there are regional identities, which connect people to the landscape and to each other. In this way, different landscape policies reflecting diverse local conditions, including the active role of local communities in modifying the landscape, are permissible within a single country provided, that they are consistent with international standards and do not conflict with one another.

Many observatories have their own organisational bodies, where local governments, civil organisations and private companies work together. This helps to find common solutions that best fit regional and local circumstances.

According to Devecchi (2015), the adoption of the European Landscape Convention (ELC) by member states has resulted in a gradual shift in terms of conceptual and political attitudes and culture toward the landscape. A key role of the landscape observatories is to increase awareness of the value of landscapes, and their role among the civil society, private organisations, and public authorities. Education is therefore an important aspect of landscape observatories. Observatories can serve as a bridge between landscape science and landscape practice, providing a real-world testing ground. This can benefit not only professionals, but also land users and the general public. The 'landscape academy,' for example, was founded in the National Landscape of Southwest Friesland in the Netherlands. An interactive educational program for visitors to the regional landscape information centre was being developed with the assistance of the University of Groningen's Centre for Landscape Studies (Veen P.J. 2015).

As a result of the Convention's emphasis on landscape awareness, promotion of education and training, is to pave the way for more mature landscape policies and involvement. The Convention aimed not only to advance the development of appropriate public policies in support of the landscape, but also to establish the principle that all European citizens should actively participate in the processes of landscape transformation in which they live. Moreover, the installation of Landscape Observatories has allowed centres to connect people. The impact varies by country and depending on the interventions chosen, but several effects have been observed. Gambino et al. (2013), for example, confirm that the Catalan Landscape Observatory has seen a positive impact of meeting centres, where expert and public knowledge about places and landscapes can be combined on a single platform for researchers, technicians, administrators, and citizens. They also recognize the significance of making it possible to help with the implementation of landscape policies, dissemination, and social communication.

The landscape observatory in Västtra Götaland (LOVG), like the Catalan Landscape Observatory, has seen an increase in landscape awareness, primarily among civil society, the local community movement, and parts of the public sector. Furthermore, the function of a regionally established platform has provided a level of legitimacy for working regionally on landscape issues and challenges. One of the most immediate and significant effects of LOVG is that the region and civil society can collaborate on issues that are important to everyone.

Landscape observatories rely heavily on data management, which also contributes to improve knowledge of landscapes. Landscape Atlases, which are conceived as operational tools for the collection, storage, and classification of data, such as images, maps, photos, GIS data, can help with this. The Atlases can serve as a foundation for identifying the values that society places on its own landscapes and, as a result, can help to encourage participation in the management of landscape resources. The tested methods are represented by

Figure 1. The data layers of LANMAP: climate, parent material, altitude and land cover. This is a pragmatic approach, taking into consideration that the available data were integrated from different data sources. Source: Múcher et al. (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2009.03.018>

the most valid Atlases on the web, where anyone can contribute to their success while also having access to them (Devecchi, 2015).

LANDSCAPE TYPES AND LAND USE

At the European level, in the "European Landscape Character Assessment Initiative" (ELCAI) project led by the Alterra research institute in the Netherlands, the practices of 14 countries have already been compared (European Commission, 2005). Within the framework of the project, landscape character areas were demarcated at the European level (Wascher, 2004; Wascher, ed. 2005) with the help of landscape indicators based on four main landscape, natural and cultural features. These features are based on an indicator typology developed on the basis of DPSIR model¹ (Kristensen, 2004).

1. Structural – describe the stock and the condition/state of landscape elements such as vegetation cover, ecosystem fragmentation, the state of ecotones
2. Functional – concern landscape processes and outputs such as changes in biodiversity, appearance of invasive species, recreational use of landscape resources
3. Management indicators – include the society's responses to landscape problems such as agri-environmental agreements, changes in the legal framework of land use, areas specially designated to landscape protection and the level of such protection
4. Value indicators – embrace everything concerning landscape quality such as aesthetic values, particular heritage sites, famous rural areas, etc.

According to the statement of European Landscape Convention, the mapping of the physical and biological properties of a landscape is no longer sufficient to identify

¹ DPSIR = Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response the causal framework for describing the interactions between society and the environment adopted by the European Environment Agency

landscape types on these measurable terms, since the subjective views, spatial experiences, expectations and desires of the population also belong to the landscape (Meeus and van den Brink, 2022). However, the characterisation and the classification based on the aforementioned, scientifically identifiable characteristics cannot be disregarded.

scale, structure and typology. What can we learn from their comparison?

Undoubtedly, the LANMAP (Mücher et al., 2010) is by far the most scientific, transparent and measurable concept, suitable to detect objective landscape units. The European

LANMAP

Level2

Arctic

- Arctic lowlands (Kl)
- Arctic hills (Kh)
- Arctic mountains (Km)

Boreal

- Boreal lowlands (Bl)
- Boreal hills (Bh)
- Boreal mountains (Bm)

Atlantic

- Atlantic lowlands (Al)
- Atlantic hills (Ah)
- Atlantic mountains (Am)

Alpine

- Alpine lowlands (Zl)
- Alpine hills (Zh)
- Alpine mountains (Zm)
- Alpine high mountains (Zn)
- Alpine alps (Za)

Mediterranean

- Mediterranean lowlands (Ml)
- Mediterranean hills (Mh)

- Mediterranean mountains (Mm)
- Mediterranean high mountains (Mn)
- Mediterranean alps (Ma)

Continental

- Continental lowlands (Cl)
- Continental hills (Ch)
- Continental mountains (Cm)
- Continental high mountains (Cn)

Anatolian

- Anatolian hills (Th)
- Anatolian mountains (Tm)
- Anatolian high mountains (Tn)
- Anatolian alps (Ta)

Steppic

- Steppic lowlands (Sl)
- Steppic hills (Sh)
- Steppic mountains (Sm)
- Steppic high mountains (Sn)

Masks

- Urban agglomerations (UR)
- Water bodies (WA)
- Intertidal flats (FL)

Figure 2. LANMAP, a Pan-European landscape classification, which covers an area of over 11 million square kilometres, expanding from Iceland in the Northwest to and including Azerbaijan in the Southeast and from Gibraltar in the Southwest to the arctic islands of Novaja Zemlja in the Northeast. Source: Mücher, 2010.

Keeping in mind, that humankind has created a wide range of landscapes, not only by changing land cover and ecosystems, but even altering landforms and hydrological conditions, rural, semi-rural, peri-urban and urban environments, the introduction of a new concept of *cultural* landscapes is needed: „A cultural landscape is a geographic area, with all its cultural and natural resources, the wildlife and domestic animals, natural and artificial ecosystems, the built and intangible heritage therein, continuously shaped by historic and present-day evolutionary processes including the adverse or beneficial impacts of human activities, social relations and evolving cultures, which mirror the evolutionary trends of human society.”² Therefore, it is no longer enough to objectively map earth, soil, water, vegetation, and climate. Including the inhabitant’s spatial experiences, expectations and desires is just as important. Although there are various maps of Europe’s landscape, they differ in sources, purpose,

Landscape Map is using the available segmentation and classification methods based on high-resolution spatial data sets / databases ensuring herewith the right balance between the acceptable reduction of the ever-inherent complexity and maintaining an adequate level of indispensable details. Mücher and his co-workers (Mücher et al. 2006; Mücher, 2010) faced a difficult task to integrate many different data sources into one comprehensive system, which resulted in a four-layer approach based on the following four key differentiating data layers (Fig. 1):

1. Climate (C). This data layer has been obtained by integration of the European Environmental Zones (EnZ) developed by Metzger et al. (2005) and the Biogeographical Regions Map of Europe (BRME), developed by Roekaerts (2002) and adopted by EEA. However, due to climate change and changes in population and land use, the Biogeographical

²SUMCULA Consortium (Sustainable Management of Cultural Landscapes) International Project Meeting, Brno, 2018

Regions Map of Europe has been updated in 2017 (EEA, 2017).

2. Altitude (A). The data layer has been obtained from the vast database of Digital Elevation Model GTOPO30, a global Digital Elevation Model with a horizontal spacing of 30 arc seconds (about 1 km), developed by USGS in 1996, but widely used (and updated) even in recent days. However, valuable information can be obtained by comparing different DEM systems, particularly when higher resolution is required (Dobre et al. 2021).

3. Parent material (P). The data layer at the time of the construction of LANMAP, was obtained by the integration of European Soil Database (ESDB, CEC, 1985), an important source of data from many other data and services are derived, containing raster (grid) data files with cell sizes of both 1km x 1km and 10km x 10km for a large number of soil related parameters. The European Soil Database (ESDB) contains four discrete datasets:

- the Soil Geographical Database of Eurasia at scale 1:1,000,000 (SGDBE)
- the Pedotransfer Rules Database (PTRDB)
- the Soil Profile Analytical Database of Europa (SPADBE)
- the Database of Hydraulic Properties of European Soils (HYPRES);

and the FAO Soil Map of the World (FAO, 1991), at a scale of 1:5 000 000, which is the only *global* overview of soil resources. These databases are continuously updated.

4. Land cover/land use (LC). This data layer has been obtained by integration of three land cover databases:

- The CORINE Land Cover (CLC) inventory, which was initiated in 1985 (Nuñez de Lima, 2005). Updates have been produced in 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018. It consists of an inventory of land cover in 44 classes. In the CORINE CLC a Minimum Mapping Unit (MMU) of 25 hectares (ha) for areal analyses and a minimum width of 100 m for linear phenomena is used.
- The GLC2000 global land cover map and database has been developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC), in partnership with 30 institutions. (Bartholomé and Belward, 2005; Mayaux et al. 2006). Recently, several global land use and land cover maps and datasets have been developed, some of them with higher resolution (Hua et al. 2018).
- PELCOM (Pan-European Land Cover Monitoring project) is a 1-km pan-European land cover map and database. The PELCOM land cover classification system consists of nine major land cover classes: forest, grassland, rainfed arable land, irrigated land, urban area, permanent ice and snow, barren land, wetlands and water bodies, all are indispensable for environmental studies (Mücher et al., 2001).

Although this landscape classification system inherently contains the impact of anthropogenic factors on the landscape considering changing landforms due to mining, agriculture, forestry, changes in landcover and, of course, settlements, the cultural approach is not sufficiently emphasized. Therefore, landscape maps and databases including more cultural dimensions have been developed.

The ELCA concept (Pedroli et al., 2013), has ample amount of the previously missed cultural sensitivity, with particular emphasis on regional traditions and landscape perceptions. This new concept captures a great deal of the multi-faceted diversity of the European landscape, based on two principles:

- The cultural landscape shall have a unique toponym originating from the perception of people.
- The toponym and the landscape should be known both in the country (or at least in its capital) and even internationally.

Such toponyms will refer to some key identifiers, of substantial diversity, embracing language, unique landscape character shaped by natural processes, human activities such as agricultural cultivation systems, settlement structures, unique buildings, historical events, natural phenomena, geographical position, ethnicity, in many cases carrying the heritage of several centuries. The ELCA toponyms can also yield clues to the genesis of cultural landscapes. The development of this concept resulted in a complex approach, considering the unity of both a sustainability and a public participation agenda in combination with quantitative methods of socio-ecological assessments and qualitative aspects of cultural values and their perception by the stakeholders (Marine, N. 2022). Thus, the “space and place” concept (Fig. 3), proposed by several researchers (Hunziker et al. 2007), has been adopted by the European Landscape Convention (2019).

Figure 3. The Space and Place concept according to Hunziker et al. (2019).

The “Space” component is the physical characteristics of the landscape, which include the urban structure, the peri-urban environment, landforms, land cover, surface waters, soils, agricultural areas, infrastructure, etc. These well understood components are usually overwhelmingly represented in landscape monitoring (Cassatella and Peano, 2011) and constitute an integral part of the landscape ecology literature and the ecosystem service framework (and, of course, constitute the basis of the LANMAP as well). The concept of “Place” embraces the perceptions and the landscape-related value system of people, which is also covered in the modern conception as cultural ecosystem services where the aesthetic, recreational and spiritual values of cultural landscapes are assessed.

FUNCTIONS AND CHALLENGES FOR LANDSCAPE OBSERVATORIES – APPLIED EARTH SYSTEM SCIENCE AS A TOOL

Several good practices in connection with landscape observatories show that truly effective decision support, planning applicability and applications can only be achieved if we do not expect a specific book-like result. From the point of view of landscape observatory functions, the definition of the landscape character should be interpreted as a process, which is spatially more and more detailed and moving forward in time through monitoring the changes and modelling landscape processes.

Functions in detail

Landscape observatories are multifunctional, scientific, social, cultural but politically independent, professional organisations (Gambino et al. 2015). Thus, further developing the above mentioned concept of Casatella and Larcher (2017) by unifying the different categories, truly multifunctional, effectively and efficiently operating landscape observatories should have the following functions:

1. Developing and maintaining a communication network between government bodies, municipalities, education system (including higher education institutions), civil society organizations, research institutes, companies, and trade organisations
2. Long-term monitoring of changes of landscape and social structures, and the ecological consequences of human activities
3. Increasing the knowledge base in all layers of society regarding cultural landscapes and their sustainable development through:
 - a. information
 - b. education (informal and formal)
 - c. regional and international networking
4. Encouraging cooperation between stakeholder groups through analysing existing and potential interactions between them
5. Landscape - resource assessment databases (“data container” – as previously mentioned) in terms of:
 - a. natural resources and ecosystems
 - b. ecological status and biodiversity
 - c. ecological vulnerability
 - d. agriculture, forestry, and fishery

- e. industry and enterprise structures
 - f. tourism and destination management
 - g. land use and land use changes
 - h. built heritage and settlement structures,
 - i. intangible heritage
 - j. demography, age distribution and population dynamics (migration)
 - k. human resources for regional and local development
6. Classification of human activities affecting the landscape
 7. Decision support systems for regional and local planners and political decision makers
 8. Enhancing the establishment of operational routines for natural resource management
 9. Adaptation of administration to landscape resources taking into account the carrying capacity of ecosystems
 10. Conservation and pragmatic utilization of heritage resources
 11. Development of infrastructure through sustainable use of ecosystem services – a regenerative approach
 12. Constant monitoring and feedback-assessment
 13. Enhancing regional and local product development - product structure and shortening supply changes
 14. Enhancing ecological, economic, and social stability

Challenges

Although the observatories have had many positive effects, some have also encountered problems that can be difficult to overcome. In Sweden, for example, municipalities have a planning monopoly, which means they are not required to collaborate with other municipalities or the region. This necessitates dysfunctional silo planning that fails to recognize wholeness and solutions at the landscape level. The Västtra Götaland region does not serve as a regional planning body. The County Administrative Board works with green infrastructure, while the region works with traditional infrastructure in collaboration with other authorities. These two planning perspectives, along with other physical planning, must be met in order for the landscape to be functionally physical planned.

Another challenge is lack of finances that makes it hard to maintain the long-term operation of a landscape observatory. In for example the Netherlands, some landscape observatories met challenges with budget cuts and no clear agreements on how provinces and regions would pick up their new responsibilities, (Veen P.J., 2015). According to Veen, P.J, many National Landscapes needed to rethink the continued work with the observatories and looked for new ways of funding and working. One way to address the challenges was to establish Service Net National Landscapes that supported regional organisations that could work to achieve the common goals.

Applied Earth System Science as a tool

One of the main problems with ‘everyday sustainability’ is the lack of system-thinking and the lack of regenerative approach. The theoretical background for regenerative sustainable development is undoubtedly Earth System Science, the application of system science to the Earth, a

fairly new concept coined by Francis Bretherton and co-workers of NASA's Earth System Science Committee in the 1980s. The increasing need of international disciplinary integration was realised by the International Council for Science (ICSU) in 1986 through the formation of the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP), linked to the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP), constructed in 1980. IGBP was originally aimed at studies of the biogeochemical cycle processes of Earth System, creating new projects such as PAGES (past global changes) and GAIM (Global Analysis, Interpretation and Modelling). This development resulted in the transformation of interdisciplinary research into transdisciplinary research where the boundaries between disciplines are far less pronounced strengthening herewith a complex system approach (Steffen et al. 2020). The 2005 World Summit Outcome Document identifies the "interrelated and mutually reinforcing pillars" of sustainable development as one integrated system, where economic and social development and environmental protection are embedded in each other: the economy is a subsystem of society, and society is a subsystem of the ecosystem.

Figure 4. The classical, simplified Bretherton diagram, illustrating the interactions between the geosphere and the biosphere, where human activity is an external force, which affects the whole system. Source: Steffen et al. 2020.

Thus, there are two conditions for the development and survival of self-sustaining systems. One is that the elements of the system interact and are in balance with each other. It is often enough that the elements interact with their immediate neighbours. The nature of the interaction can be both cohesive and repulsive, but in the long-term cohesion and balance must prevail (Stansberry et al. 2019). The other condition is that the system must be open, i. e. interact with the environment. A self-sustaining system must be in close contact with the environment, with which it exchanges material and energy. These are actually subsystems within the unity of society and nature such as the sustainable use of land in agricultural production, the sustainability of cities, the way (process) of the production of certain products, the sustainability of societies, etc. It is also obvious, that Applied earth System Science is nothing else, than the practice sustainable development from a regenerative point of view, an indispensable tool for landscape management and the basis for all functions of landscape observatories.

INTERNATIONAL GOOD PRACTICES AND THEIR ADAPTABILITY

There are different types of landscape observatories (as discussed above) and even organisations and institutions with landscape observatory functions such as monitoring of landscapes and maintaining databases. It is important to review international good practices, either directly concerning already existing landscape observatories or landscape observatory functions at different organisations in Europe. Many of these have good practices, which can be adapted and used in a new, universally applicable landscape observatory concept. First, we will analyse already existing, well known landscape observatories and experimental ones followed by some other cases, where some landscape observatory functions are practiced, which may be a good start for the establishment of fully functional landscape observatories in the future.

A cross-border spatial data infrastructure (SDI)

The IDE OTALEX C Local Landscape Units (Spain-Portugal Cross Border region), is the first cross-border spatial data infrastructure (SDI), a Territorial and Environmental Landscape Observatory of Alentejo, Extremadura and Centro, consisting of different databases, which contain environmental, social and economic indicators (Batista et al, 2013). This landscape observatory is working through decision support systems, based on the Local Landscape Units (LLU) Concept. A Local Landscape Unit is the smallest landscape mapping unit, at local management and planning scale, built on the following key variables:

- lithology
- geomorphology
- soil
- land use
- land cover

Figure 5. The OTALEX C project area, the territory of the first cross-border SDI. Source: www.ideotalex.eu

The LLU is based on maps of Land Cover (LC), Geology and a customised GIS application for semi-automated landform classification (Weiss, 2001) the TPI - Topographic Position Index. The observatory has a multilingual (Portuguese, Spanish and English) geoportal, which integrates a Map viewer, Metadata Catalogue and Gazetteer.

Regional landscape observatory

In Italy, the Landscape Observatory of Veneto aims to promote the protection, management and regenerative development of the landscapes of the Veneto region. This include the integration of the landscape into territorial, urban and sector planning policies and in those of economic, cultural, environmental, agricultural and social nature which may have a direct or indirect impact on the landscape. Furthermore, the observatory developed a wide range of education programmes both for professionals and for the general public.

Figure 6. Relief map of the Veneto region in Italy. Source: <https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Veneto>

The observatory extends its activity to the whole regional territory, to natural, rural, urban and peri-urban spaces. It deals both with landscapes that can be considered exceptional, and with landscapes of 'everyday life' with particular attention to degraded landscapes.

The observatory informs about its activities according to the principles established by the European Landscape Convention and in compliance with the provisions of Legislative Decree 42/04, and in particular promotes:

- the protection of the landscape aimed at recognizing, safeguarding and, where necessary, recovering the cultural values that it expresses, with particular attention to the aspects and characteristics of the landscape that are representative of the Venetian identity and expression of cultural values;

- the enhancement of the landscape through specific knowledge, information, requalification and fruition activities.

The Region, through the observatory, in addition to the protection and enhancement of the Veneto landscapes promotes:

- sensitization of civil society, private organizations and public authorities to the value of landscapes, their role and their transformation
- the training of specialists in the field of knowledge and intervention on landscapes also through the launch of multidisciplinary training programs for professionals in the public and private sector and for interested trade associations;
- scholastic and university teachings that deal, within the respective disciplines, with the values associated with the landscape and with issues concerning its protection, management and planning;
- procedures for the participation of the public, local authorities and other subjects involved in the definition and implementation of landscape policies.

The Landscape Observatory of Catalonia

The Landscape Observatory of Catalonia is probably the best developed and structured landscape observatory in Europe, a well-established advisory body of the Government of Catalonia and a communication platform, education and information centre for the Catalan society in general regarding all possible aspects of landscape (Martí, 2021). The organisation form of the Landscape Observatory is consortium, which is included in the Act for protection, management and planning of the landscape in Catalonia. The consortium gained legal status on the 30th of November 2004 and its constitution was published in the Government of Catalonia Official Gazette (Resolution PTO/3386/2004). The main purposes of the Landscape Observatory is to increase public awareness and knowledge about the Catalan landscapes among its people, and enhance the application of the European Landscape Convention in Catalonia. Therefore, the Landscape Observatory became the meeting point between the Government of Catalonia, regional and local authorities, research institutes and universities, non-governmental organisations and professional groups and all other parts of the Catalan society, concerning the management and conservation of the landscape.

The other important function of the Landscape Observatory is the continuous monitoring of landscape evolution, environmental status, changes of landscape character, social conditions, even demography and settlement patterns through a vast number of observation points. Furthermore, the observatory also serves as a reference base for the scientific and technical research of the Catalan landscape.

Figure 7. The landscape map of Catalonia. The historical landscapes of outstanding cultural value are marked with blue colour. Sources: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-20345071> and <http://www.catpaisatge.net/pahiscat/eng/estudi.php#!prettyPhoto/0/>

Since 2005, the Landscape Observatory has been working on the complete catalogue of the Catalan landscape types, which resulted in the new roadmap called CATPAISATGE 2020. The new strategy of the Landscape Observatory is mirrored in the slogan of CATPAISATGE 2020 “Country, Landscape, Future”, a holistic approach embracing the main issues of landscape conservation such as internationalisation, local and entrepreneurial development, identification of new landscapes, the importance of cultural values, research, and communication (Martí, 2021). The research has been organised into ten key areas:

1. Internationalisation instead of singularity

Internationalisation is of key importance not only for this landscape observatory but for the international scientific community as well, taking into consideration the fact, that Catalonia has one of the greatest landscape-diversity of Europe. However, successful landscape conservation requires the maintenance of the identity of these landscapes. It is also worth to mention, that the Landscape Observatory of Catalonia has one of the most comprehensive and complete landscape catalogues in Europe.

2. Living and producing in quality surroundings

Outstanding landscape quality is a prerequisite for the country's international profile, competitiveness of the territories in terms of attracting investments, skilled labour, and innovation. Furthermore, high quality local products and local distribution networks are closely related to both landscape quality and heritage conservation.

3. Landscape, creativity, and strategic sectors

The uniqueness and quality of the landscape is crucial for some sectors of strategic importance such as agriculture, tourism and hospitality, gastronomy, entertainment services, local trades and crafts, etc. Spoiled or mediocre landscape do not attract tourists, and they cannot even keep their own population.

4. Landscape and the local world

As previously mentioned, landscapes with a strong identity greatly contribute to the development of local economies, they are able to keep their population and attract more people due to a strong self-esteem and quality of life.

5. The creation of new benchmark landscapes

Catalonia is rich in benchmark landscapes, those, which have a strong symbolic and cultural significance, an iconic status, gained in many cases during centuries. However, there are many 'ordinary' landscapes, which are presently overlooked but have a great potential to be developed into benchmark landscapes of reference through a participatory approach, reaching all the stakeholders concerned.

6. Landscape, values, and community

A very important task of the landscape observatory is to raise and strengthen the public awareness of the natural and cultural diversity of the landscape. A strong identity will increase the possibilities to establish a strong and cohesive community.

7. Landscape, employment, and entrepreneurship

The landscape, through its wealth of natural and human resources, generates economic potential in those sectors, which are linked to the territory and its ecosystem services. Wide range of employment opportunities may arise in agriculture, local food production, industry, tourism, and even in creative fields such as art, cinema, fashion, gastronomy, etc.

8. Climate change, energy, and landscape

Landscape is an excellent indicator to recognise the impact of climate change in terms of changes in water resources, land cover, soil fertility, appearance of invasive species and overall changes in land character. Observing these impacts, the prediction of future scenarios will be possible as well as strategies for mitigation of adverse effects of climate change, including energy production, in creasing the share of renewable energy in the energy mix to reduce GHG emissions.

9. Research and innovation as growing values

The unwritten competition between nations of the next millennium will be won by the country that can provide its residents with an environment and landscape that encourages creativity. The unique landscape value lends character to the Hungarian landscape and stimulates creativity. Landscape research will have to address landscape changes, ecosystem services, reinforce the potential for the creation of new employment opportunities in existing and newly emerging sectors.

10. Education and communication

Landscape education is one of the central activities of a landscape observatory, since this requires a particularly strong transdisciplinary approach, deep knowledge in Earth System Science, landscape ecology, natural resources, ecosystem resiliency, heritage science, economics with emphasis on circular economy and social sciences with a practical approach. Furthermore, taking into consideration the wide range of stakeholders concerned, the education and communication programmes must be well adapted to the target groups to reach all stakeholder groups. Communication and continuous informal education through a number of available channels and event organisation concerning landscape conservation and landscape values is crucial for the involvement of the regional and local population.

Landscape catalogue of Hungary

Interesting case is the first Landscape Character Identifier in Hungary, which has been developed within the project called "Strategic studies establishing the long-term preservation and development of natural values of public importance and the domestic implementation of the objectives of the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2020" coordinated by the Ministry of Agriculture (Agrárminisztérium, 2021). The project had four important research topics:

1. mapping of National Ecosystem Services,
2. examination of Natura 2000 areas,
3. exploration of the domestic green infrastructure planning,
4. analysis of the country's landscape character.

The Landscape Character Identifier contains a summary description of the elements of the methodology developed in the Landscape Character project element. According to our current knowledge, the analysis solutions presented in this programme are the most appropriate, suitable for continuing the landscape character delimitation, description and evaluation that has already begun. The experts participating in the work recommend this methodology for further use to landscape professionals who will perform landscape character analysis in the future, either in the framework of additional national projects or in work for regional research, planning, protection, or development purposes. It can also be recommended to decision-makers working in professional administration and public administration and to employees of civil organizations whose activities are linked to shaping the landscape and preserving its values. Such preparatory work provide and excellent basis for the development of landscape

observatories in Hungary, one of which is being planned in Transdanubia, the western part of the country.

Other organisations (NGOs) for landscape conservation

There are numerous civil organisations specialized on landscape conservation with substantial international network and scientific base. The three most important organisations are CIVILSCAPE, UNISCAPE and ECOS.

CIVILSCAPE is an international federation, which was established on the 28th of February 2008 in Florence, at the beginning representants from six countries and during the first five years another 28 countries joined the organisation. Today CIVILSCAPE consists of 132 civil society organizations, public institutions and economic actors from 32 countries. The purpose of CIVILSCAPE is to promote sustainable and regenerative landscape management, according to the European Landscape Convention.

UNISCAPE is a European Network of Universities specialised on landscape research and education. The founding members of UNISCAPE are 42 universities from Italy, Slovenia, France, Spain, Portugal, the Netherlands, Belgium and Slovakia which has grown substantially during the last years and today consists of 56 university members from 15 European Countries and 2 private foundations. The aim of this network is to promote and develop transdisciplinary research and education according to the objectives and principles of the European Landscape Convention regarding landscape ecology, evolution and transformation and landscape conservation. Furthermore, UNISCAPE is continuing the ATLAS project, which established a database concerning the current educational provision in landscape issues, land use and environmental impact assessment at different educational levels throughout Europe.

Although ECOS European Environmental Protection Civil Organizations for the Civil Association for Standardization, is not directly working with landscape character and landscape conservation, it aims to enforce environmental protection aspects in the European standards being prepared. Particularly important the role of ECOS in landscape protection in terms of waste management and preparation for reuse and material-efficient recycling in policies and standards, at the same time making sure that waste prevention strategies such as eliminating or reducing landfills are prioritised. ECOS conducts scientific and lobbying activities, maintains contact with the EU administration, and disseminates information through the civil and standardization organizations of the member countries. Its experts are present in the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC).

CASE STUDY: LANDSCAPE OBSERVATORY VÄSTRA GÖTALAND, SWEDEN

Landscape Observatory Västra Götaland (LOVG) was established in 2019 as a two-year long pilot project in southwestern Sweden. The goal was to establish a

collaborative platform with various actors in order to strengthen the role of the landscape in the region. The Region of Västra Götaland (Fig. 8) has been designated as the coordinator of the observatory because cultural development and natural heritage are regional responsibilities. Collaborative partners are the University of Gothenburg, Mariestad Municipality, the County Administration Board, and Skaraborg subregion. Nonetheless, residents' input and planning based on a holistic understanding of the landscape's values have been prioritized.

Figure 8. The map of Västra Götaland County and its location in Sweden. Source: Wikipedia

LOVG focus on operational activities and utilizes at least three practical case studies to evaluate collaborative models, develop declarations of intent with partners, mapping competence, develop an information platform, and document work processes. Additionally, the work will result in a proposal for the organisation and management of a subsequent long-term business. Recent LOVG priorities include maintaining an active dialogue with the collaborators and contributing to children and young people's understanding of the landscape's diverse values, including natural and cultural environmental values, as well as societal values. Additionally, the focus has been on continuing to develop collaboration with the academy.

LOVG intends to complement and support various sectors in the work of regional development. As examples, the connections between city and country, as well as water management, are mentioned. Culture is also described as playing an important role in a broader sense of natural and cultural heritage. The objective is to supplement and support increased cooperation and coordination that leads to solutions in a variety of landscape issues. The administration will coordinate the work with the Landscape Observatory Västra

Götaland, which will be part of regular operations. Priorities during the period 2022 - 2024 focus on resident influence and planning based on a holistic view of the landscape's values. The work presupposes collaboration with other actors.

LOVG had three case studies during the pilot project period. These three have been crucial in situating LOVG in a regional context and exchanging knowledge about landscape work in the region. The first case is the development of LAB190 - a project based on a 70-kilometer-long road that connects Gothenburg and Nossebro through four municipalities. The work's goal is to connect city and country through a holistic view of the landscape. In the landscape along Route 190, they strive to unite a vibrant business community, strengthened ecosystems, and social well-being. Rural areas near cities have a unique opportunity to lead and serve as a role model for how the landscape can be used in a long-term sustainable way that fosters interaction. Involved stakeholders take the lead and are at the forefront of issues concerning long-term societal development. LAB190 creates the landscape in a holistic and collaborative manner across municipal and sector boundaries.

The second case is Geopark Skaraborg, that brings together regional and municipal governments, as well as civil society, with the goal of establishing a Geopark for Västergötland's plateau mountains, with formal recognition from UNESCO. The Geopark has become the first global geopark (<https://www.platabergensgeopark.se/>).

The group's long-term goal is to increase children's and young people's participation and involvement in the local natural and cultural heritage through the development of pedagogy that is based, for example, on digitalization and intercultural dialogue. The group was comprised of representatives from Dalsland's environmental and energy association, as well as various authorities, organizations, and entrepreneurs with a local presence in Dalsland.

LOVG also has a data and mapping-focused project called Hembygden. The historical development of a number of different areas has been mapped in collaboration with local associations. These have been supplemented by descriptions of contemporary situations that contain natural and cultural values. Finally, school classes visit the landscape and share Dalsland's Catalyst Group is the last case that assists the municipality in achieving sustainable land use and rural development. The catalyst group has started a discussion to form a Biosphere Reserve for the region in Dalsland, but the work is still at its initial phase.

The case study of Landscape observatory Västra Götaland in Sweden is based on testing and evaluating landscape challenges and how these can be addressed through landscape observatories by governance and stakeholder engagement. It is further based on personal networks with researchers, officials, and representatives from various organizations working with landscape observatories. The Landscape Observatory Documentation (LOD) conducted a thorough overview of European Landscape Observatories, which is a particularly useful source material (Cassatella & Larcher, 2017).

As a framework for the work, we use:

- ELC: CETS 176 - Draft European Landscape Convention as amended by the 2016 Protocol (coe.int)
- Recommendation ELC: 99C5FFA (coe.int)
- MANIFESTO: Manifesto on the Future of the European Landscape UNISCAPE

We employ triangulation, which refers to the use of more than one approach to investigating the research questions in order to boost confidence in the resulting findings. One of the initiators of the methodology was Webb, Campbell, Schwartz, and Sechrest (1966), who suggested, "Once a proposition has been confirmed by two or more independent measurement processes, the uncertainty of its interpretation is greatly reduced". The triangulation method combines quantitative and qualitative research, resulting in a more comprehensive set of findings. This article employs methodological triangulation, which means that we employ more than one research method to measure the same object of interest. Triangulation is a good method for verifying results while also identifying and eliminating methodological flaws, data, or investigator bias (Opperman, 2000; Pratesi, 2023). As a result, a multi-method approach allows for greater confidence in the results. Three approaches will be used to answer the research questions:

- Interviews/questionnaire to stakeholders involved in landscape observatories,
- Workshops with planning experts, decision-makers, NGOs, economic actors, etc. (e. g. a Nordic workshop organised by VGR with external experts,
- planners from the Nordics – how to organise a Nordic LO, Local workshop with planners?)
- Analysis of case studies and literature

Results

There is no doubt that protecting European landscapes, cultural heritage, and identity, as well as preventing further degradation, is critical. With today's emphasis on the United Nations' global sustainability goals and Agenda 2030, there is a compelling case for illuminating landscape changes and landscape issues from a more global perspective, taking into account the various dimensions of sustainable development, including cultural, economic, social, and environmental dimensions, as well as regional and local perspectives. Experience has shown that Landscape observatories fulfil a critical role in addressing a variety of issues relating to the protection, management, and planning of landscapes. The landscape is constantly changing, and it is necessary to monitor it and collect and disseminate information to public institutions, private partners, organizations, and civil society.

It is essential to involve a wide variety of stakeholders in addressing landscape issues, and a collaborative platform is likely to produce the desired results. Landscape observatories have proven to be helpful in this regard. Experience from e. g. LOVG in Sweden, as discussed above, also emphasise their visions for the future landscape. Following each point is a brief explanation of how the legal work relates to each priority (Table 1). Important to have a long-term platform

Priority	Topic	Legal setting
High	Create a spatial planning platform with broader engagement from public, private and civil society.	Create an organisation and legal identity at regional level.
	Increase the accessibility and participation of all residents by encouraging collaboration between natural and cultural heritage organizations and civil society for joint business development and resource utilization	Facilitation unit of multi-stakeholders' engagement in spatial planning
	Reduce the risk of in silo planning while also ensuring that critical issues in the landscape are managed and coordinated.	Enable cross-border cooperation to address landscape challenges - both regional and municipal level through strategic collaboration between the actors in the cultural environment and the relevant sectors of society
	Inspire new initiatives for sustainable landscape development	Projects established for sustainable land use
	Increase collaboration on landscape issues and strengthen interactions with research and education, and - serve as a knowledge exchange hub for national and international exchange.	New forms of knowledge exchange for sustainable spatial planning
Medium	Increase capacity to meet climate change challenges.	Climate adaptation measurements
	Contribute to children and young people's understanding of the landscape's different values, as well natural and cultural environmental values, as societal values.	Incorporate landscape values in early education
	.	Increase citizens' ability to actively participate in landscape evaluation and management.
Low	Increase the experience value for visitors and tourists by, in collaboration with the hospitality industry, coordinating sustainable natural and cultural heritage experiences and connecting visitor destinations and other cultural events.	

Table 1: Identification of key topics for the activity of the Landscape Observatory of VGR. Source: LOVG 2022, Anders M. Nilsson

(commitment), in order to gain stability and legitimacy in landscape planning. They would permit observation based on appropriate study protocols employing a variety of indicators, as well as the collection and exchange of information on policies and experience. They could be stand-alone or part of a larger observation system for coordinating existing landscape-related assignments of various regional authorities.

There are some overlaps between regional authorities that could be coordinated, for example, in Sweden, the Swedish county administrative boards are the state's extended arms in planning matters, and regional authorities, such as Region Skåne in southern Sweden who is in charge of producing

various thematic planning documents, green structure plans, regional planning strategies, and so on. The role of Landscape observatories should therefore be to support existing planning authorities and can play an important role by utilizing interlocking observation systems and allowing for ongoing exchanges. These can include, for example, describing the state of landscapes, exchanging information on policies and experiences related to landscape protection, management and planning, public participation and implementation at various levels, and developing indicators to assess the effectiveness of landscape policies.

Landscape observatories can be established at several levels – local, regional, national, and international – and experience has shown that local conditions determine which form is best suited for the area. Existing exchanges of information and experience between states, regions, and territorial communities should be based on exemplarity, but always in the context of the original landscape's political, social, ecological, and cultural context. The composition of observatories is up to the administrative bodies involved, but it should allow for collaboration between scientists, professionals, and technicians from public authorities and the general public. Uniscape En-Route (2015.A)

It appears to be obvious, that global developments such as urbanisation, climate change and growing public participation offer great challenges for the landscape everywhere, but the right solutions have to be found on the regional scale. Not only in the Netherlands but also in other countries we see that regional organisations are gaining power, while national states tend to become less important as far as environmental planning is concerned. Regions all over Europe can learn a lot from each other and the proposed Network of European Landscape Observatories could be a useful platform for exchange and cooperation. (UNISCAPE En-Route - a. I - n. 1 – 2015). In conclusion, the study demonstrates that the following areas are critical to ensuring the sustainability of landscape observatories:

- A landscape observatory needs to create a more stable structure for involvement and activities from stakeholders.
- Lessons from several LOs in Europe highlight the importance of a public organisation's ownership and management
- Importance of public involvement to ensure involvement of the civil society in development projects.

A CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR THE OPTIMAL STRUCTURE OF LANDSCAPE OBSERVATORIES – A TRANSDISCIPLINARY MULTIFUNCTIONAL APPROACH

The wide range of functions of landscape observatories require a flexible and dynamic structure, which is in principle adaptable to any environment, making the establishment of a future international landscape observatory network possible. In our opinion, the most effective and efficient structure of a landscape observatory should be constructed not only on the principles of applied Earth System Science, but applying the substantially extended forms of the DPSIR (Driving forces, Pressures, States, Impacts and Responses) Framework, which is dealing more with the social and cultural dimensions of landscape management (Kristensen, 2004, Szlavik, 2013; Gupta et al. 2020; Allen, 2022). Society, the economy and the environment form a complex system through their multifaceted interactions, and the use of the DPSIR model helps to understand and analyse the connections in this system (Bradley and Yee, 2015). The cycle of the model shows how socio-economic processes (driving forces) influence and burden the state of the environment and what response measures are necessary to change the driving forces and to prevent and reduce the burdens (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. The cycles of the DPSIR model, a framework of a dynamic environmental assessment and management model. Source: <https://encyclopedia.pub/entry/1535>

This is particularly well applicable to the landscape if we approach sustainable and regenerative development from a landscape and ecosystem perspective, including the cultural and psycho-social dimensions as well.

Drivers / driving forces (D): main social and economic processes influencing the state of the environment, motivate the activities of citizens, satisfy basic – and often changing – human needs, and shaping social relations:

- social values, lifestyle, consumption patterns
- economic activities (e. g. industry, agriculture, transport, energy use, water management, waste management)
- specific territorial needs
- regulatory and institutional systems
- ecological footprint depending on the aforementioned activities.

The spatial distribution, intensity and size of these driving forces vary, they can originate from different sources and act locally, regionally or globally. It is also important to point out the factors, which are not driving forces, such as:

- Climate and weather, natural events which change the state of the environment (e.g., extreme weather phenomena, sea level rise, volcanism, global climate change). In the DPSIR terminology, driving forces are specified as actions to fulfil human needs while the natural forcing mechanisms, which are defined in Earth System Science are not included here (therefore, applied Earth System Science and the DPSIR Framework *together* will constitute the scientific basis of a new landscape observatory model).
- Any type of “management” (e.g., water management, waste management) – these are responses.
- Human population – this is actually reflected in human state and is a direct result of Social Driving Forces.

Since the driving forces within the DPSIR framework are mainly of economic and social nature, Bradley and Yee (2015) defined two intimately interacting categories, Economic and Social Driving Forces (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Driving Forces in the DPSIR Framework. Source: Redrawn and modified after Bradley and Lee (2015).

Pressure (P): these are human activities, being attributed to social and economic driving forces which can be divided into two main categories, either inducing environmental changes or human behaviour, resulting in adverse impact on Human health. Thus, the two categories are environmental pressures and human behaviour pressures.

Environmental pressures

- discharge of physical, chemical, and/or biological agents into the environment
- overexploitation of natural resources through direct contact uses such as drainage of wetlands, regulation of riverbeds, dredging, overfishing, clear cutting, extensive deforestation, creation of artificial habitats, etc.
- changes in land use and spatial structure, such as conversion of green areas / nature protected areas into “brown” territories for building or establishment of heavy industries; changing natural ecosystems into intensive, “industrial” agriculture; fragmentation of natural ecosystems, etc.

Human behaviour pressures

- Self-Care includes activities for the maintenance of personal health and well-being such as:
 - Nutrition and diet (selection of food, healthy diet)
 - Personal hygiene
 - Household routines
 - Choice of medical care (disease prevention or receiving in-time diagnosis through screening, vaccinations)
- Lifestyle is the summary of all personal choices and decisions, which might contribute to illness, death or survival and includes:
 - Choice of transportation from the point of view of public health
 - Choice of housing (in means of availability and economic conditions)
 - Consumption patterns (e.g., overeating)
 - Purchasing habits, use of resources and recycling
 - Risky sexual behaviours
 - Use or abuse of tobacco, alcohol, drugs

- Sport and other physical exercise
- Sun exposure
- Mobility and travel behaviour is greatly influenced by location, the availability and standard of infrastructure, land use mix, residential density, the time necessary to commute between destinations.

State (S): the state includes the natural and built environmental elements and their systems, processes, and structures and the human systems:

Natural and built environmental elements

- air quality – degree and types of pollution
- water quality – quality of surface waters, ground water quality and availability, availability of good quality drinking water and suitable water for irrigation
- soil quality – soil types and soil biota, degree, and types of soil degradation
- the state of the living world: biodiversity and ecosystem status, assessment of ecological carrying capacity
- man-made built structures and artificial ecosystems, which constitute important parts of human habitats

The state of human systems

The state of human systems include human health conditions for a given population, other population-level attributes including distribution (age, economic status, race, education, gender), population density, demographics, and attributes on the individual level such as age, sex, individual health conditions.

Impact (I): The effect of the environmental condition, which means changes in the functioning of ecosystems, can have adverse impact:

- on human health and generally human well-being
- on ecosystems and ecosystem services
- on the stability of the climate

Responses (R): measures resulting in the improvement of the state of the environment and the reduction of adverse effects or the mitigation of the impact of these adverse effects through:

- elimination of environmentally hazardous activities
- increasing the share of renewable energy and nuclear energy (where possible and appropriate) in the energy mix
- introducing and supporting the establishment of local and regional energy production systems
- conversion to precision, multifunctional and organic agriculture
- applying sustainable waste management systems aiming at the realization of the ‘reuse and zero landfill’ concept
- restoring ecosystem status through remediation and regenerative measures such as wetland restoration or re-introduction of endemic plant species where appropriate
- controlling invasive species
- improving environmental legislation
- increasing public awareness concerning environmental problems through a participatory approach

- shortening product and raw material supply chains where possible
- enhancing local production and creating economic viability for local products through local and regional distribution chains
- applying nature-based solutions in infrastructure development

The environmental, economic, social, historic and cultural constituents of landscapes form one holistic system, which must be treated as one system, and can be understood and managed only through a transdisciplinary and ecosystem centred approach. Therefore, landscape observatories can be excellent tools to manage changes and to ensure a regenerative and sustainable development. Recently, as described above, there are different types and organisation forms of landscape observatories, but in order to achieve a well-functioning European or even global network, one comprehensive, transdisciplinary, manageable and to many conditions adaptable structure and function system is required. Therefore, we propose a conceptual model for landscape observatories, which is taking into consideration the whole (both natural and human) environment in a flexible and adaptable way by jointly applying Earth System Science and the above described DPSIR framework.

Concerning the analysis of impacts on ecosystem status there is an interesting approach, which is close to our conception in terms of integrating natural and social factors, this is the holistic DPSCR₄ (Drivers–Pressures–Stressors–Condition–Responses) framework, which includes even the environmental stressors (Harwell et al. 2019), a comprehensive conceptual model of the coupled human–ecological system. It can be useful, to directly include natural factors among the drivers and integrate the stressors as key components into the human ecological system, since risk assessment of changes will be easier to carry out even on landscape level, and the central action of the remediation measures is the removal of the stressors (Fig. 11). Thus, this system is a further extension and holistic modification of the DPSIR framework, which gives additional clues to the construction of a dynamic landscape observatory model.

This complex approach is necessary, because of the above described very wide functions of a landscape observatory. The conceptual model is suitable to capture, visualize and organise key factors in a complex system, making hereby possible to evaluate the consequences of changes in such system, by linking anthropogenic and natural environmental factors to ecosystem conditions. This will contribute to a shared understanding of system dynamics and the appreciation of the diversity and the value of information.

Figure 11. The Drivers – Pressures – Stressors – Condition – Responses (DPSRC₄) conceptual framework, where drivers are interpreted holistically, including natural drivers together with demographic, social and economic driving factors, and stressors are included into the coupled human – ecological system, where the key action of remediation measures is to remove the existing stressors. Source: Harwell et al. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4152>

This information is necessary to identify the most important performance indicators in terms of scientific research, creation of databases, range of services, social functions and conservation of landscapes approached from an evolutionary perspective, taking into consideration the changes of natural and social environment caused by both natural and anthropogenic factors. Furthermore, due to the involvement of numerous stakeholders, the formation, development and function of a landscape observatory is also a collaborative learning process, which shall be regarded as a major tangible product of landscape observatories.

- Establish efficient communication:
 - Among decision-makers
 - Among scientists and program staff
 - Between scientists and decision-makers
 - With the general public
- Support the decision making of local and regional authorities and government organisations through advisory services and well-established decision support systems and tailored education programmes (competence development – when and where required)
- Establish, expand, and maintain international scientific,

THE FUNCTIONAL ANATOMY OF A MULTIFUNCTIONAL LANDSCAPE OBSERVATORY

Figure 12. The conceptual model – the functional anatomy of an effectively and efficiently working landscape observatory. In the centre the connected key functions are maintained from the databases, which supply all information needed for the operation. Obviously, monitoring and research together keep the databases always updated. Source: own design.

This conceptual model (Fig. 12) shall be a universal mall for the structure and functions of all landscape observatories, adaptable to any natural and social environment, only by adjusting the proportions of the system at the appropriate scales. Therefore, the model will be able to:

- Assess resources, construct inventories and handle a wide range of databases;
- Formalize and interpret system processes and dynamics;
- Identify linkages of processes across disciplinary boundaries;
- Monitor the changes of ecological, social, demographic, cultural and economic state of the landscape;
- Predict the consequences of changes in the system;
- Identify the connections and scope of the system of interest;
- Acquire and integrate new information into the existing systems;

innovation and development platform and knowledge bank through active networking in order to intensify knowledge transfer and promote exchange of international good practices;

- Developing formal and informal education programmes adapted to local and regional conditions but emphasizing their global relevance.

CONCLUSIONS

Landscape-related tasks require a horizontal approach and intervention. From a sustainability point of view, landscape-related tasks exist in one system, which is why only a system-level answer can be given to them. At the beginning of the implementation of the European Landscape Convention, in many countries, implementation often began along fragmented government structures and sectors and by arbitrarily distribution of the tasks. However, managing

ecosystem related tasks in a non-complex manner is not efficient.

There are several good practices today for landscape management and conservation, but a complex international solution is still missing. Landscape observatories have been created in several places, but their systems, structures and routines are quite different, even if the common goal is to implement the strategies outlined in the European Landscape convention. One of the best and effectively functioning landscape observatories today is the Landscape Observatory of Catalonia, which can be regarded as one model system, which is based on the conservation of both natural and cultural landscape values. However, in our opinion, learning from the success of this landscape observatory, a new, internationally universally applicable model might be necessary taking advantage from Earth System Sciences and the DPSIR and DPSRC₄ conceptual frameworks.

Very often economic and sociological approaches are dominant and the natural basis of the landscape, global change issues, and the complexity of the ecosystem services are not sufficiently addressed on system level. The new approach is therefore based on a dynamic and interactive landscape observatory model, where the functions of inventory making, database creation, environmental and socio-economic modelling, ecosystem monitoring, research, formal and informal education, advisory services, policy development, public information, event organisation and international networking constitute one system.

One of the most important tasks of landscape observatories, to assist by advisory services local and regional authorities and government organisations in enforcing the requirements of sustainability for all policy areas, in order for the sustainable treatment of natural and cultural resources and the protection of the landscape to be integrated into the public consciousness and become part of the social value system.

Landscape observatories can be harmonized into a multiscale and multilayer level approach of different yet compatible ecosystem networks as garden (individual scale), or regional landscape observatories (middle scale) while a system of communicating landscape observatories might function as an earth observatory (global scale).

Among the area-specific goals, important are the creation of a city network ensuring a multi-centred spatial structure, increasing the capacity of rural areas to support the population, regenerating and, where needed, creating urban ecosystems through green infrastructures, nature-based solutions and urban agriculture, and the development of areas of outstanding landscape value.

Policy goals should include the creation of viable regions identified as areas of intervention to achieve a specific goal: strengthening the role of nature, landscape and environmental protection, preserving biological diversity, preserve and enhance value-based development of rural heritage, the landscape, social, management and architectural values of rural areas, the nurturing traditions and strengthening local identity.

The new landscape observatory should be a value-preserving, resilient and at the same time innovative, transdisciplinary collaboration platform, multifunctional knowledge centre for landscape thinking and decision-making in a given region, enhancing nature and cultural heritage conservation and socio-economic viability.

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